

VI International Forum on Teacher Education

Relationship of Economic and Educational Factors of the Educational Environment of the School with Indicators of the Psychological Well-being of the Teacher

Rezeda M. Khusainova*

Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street, rezedakhusainova@mail.ru

Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the peculiarities of the psychological well-being of teachers from different learning environments. The purpose of the study is to examine the satisfaction with life those teachers' who work in schools with a high economic or educational rating. The theoretical basis of the study was the work of Bredburn (1969) and Shiryaeva (2008). It has been established that teachers are equally satisfied with their lives, regardless of the rating of the school where they work. It was found that for teachers from schools with a high economic rating, the subjective value of professional activity is more significant than for teachers from schools with a high educational rating. The higher the indicators of such spheres as independence and physical well-being are, the higher the involved position of the teacher in solving problems in both studied groups.

However, for teachers from schools with a high economic rating, social support, and personal convictions are also important. While for teachers from schools with a high educational rating, it is necessary to experience positive emotions and be able to study. The sense of mental stability and balance is interconnected with the psychological sphere in the group of teachers from schools with a high economic rate. At the same time, teachers from schools with a high educational rating have this relationship with all spheres of life - the physical sphere, the psychological sphere, the level of independence, social relationships, the environment, the spiritual sphere. Accordingly, the mental resistance of the teacher's group from high educational rating schools to problems is possible in the condition of their overall psychological well-being.

Keywords: psychological well-being, teacher, Quality of Life, educational environment, economic school rating, educational school rating.

© 2020 Rezeda M. Khusainova

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. E-mail: rezedakhusainova@mail.ru

Introduction

The relevance of the research problem

The effectiveness of the educational environment that sets the system of social relations depends on the coherence in the interaction between the components of the educational environment of the school which is defined both by the characteristics of the environment itself and by the characteristics of the subject included in this environment. The structure of the educational environment includes several levels: the macro level (educational environment of the country), the meso-level (regional, municipal, institutional), the micro level (individual) (Ivanova, 2015; Gilemkanova, 2017).

Researchers (Gilemkanova, 2019; Volkov, 2016; Rating of the regions of the Russian Federation on quality of life, 2016, 2017), emphasize that the educational environment depends on “immaterial resources”, which are peculiar criteria in determining the rating of educational organizations. So, for example, the criteria for rating determining of the best Russian schools in 2017 were the results of the 9th grade final exams, the results of the regional and final stages of the All-Russian Olympiad for schoolchildren, the participation of students in the All-Russian verification work. In this case, as a rule, more often we are talking about schoolchildren and, to a much lesser extent, teachers who organize and accompany the educational process (Bagnetova, Pisareva, & Ponomareva, 2015). This situation gives rise to the relevance of studying the quality of life and psychological well-being of a teacher included in professional activities.

The quality of interaction largely depends on the important figure of the educational process - the teacher, and not only on his/her professional activity and competence, but also on his/her psychological well-being.

Purpose and objectives of the study

To study and describe the features of the quality of life and psychological well-being of teachers from schools with a high economic and high educational rating

Literature review

The theoretical basis of the study are the works of Bradburn (1969), who is the first to present data from surveys of large samples aimed at measuring the Quality of Life and thus has laid the theoretical basis for understanding the phenomenon of psychological well-being, which is identified with the subjective feeling of happiness and overall satisfaction with life (Evans, 2006; Pavlotskaya, 2016) as well as Shiryaeva's works, who proposes to consider psychological well-being "as a set of personal resources, ensuring the subjective and objective personal success in the "subject-environment" system (2008). A close concept to psychological well-being is subjective

well-being (Filonenko & Yakovleva, 2018). In the works of Diener (1999, 2002), well-being is described as a subjective concept which depends on such objective conditions as health, income, and literacy.

A number of studies describe the features of psychological and subjective well-being in a professional environment. So Filonenko and Yakovleva (2018) studied the factors and components of the subjective well-being of scientific and pedagogical workers of universities. The authors denote that “the structure of the teachers’ well-being characterizes their activity largely than in other professions” (Filonenko & Yakovleva, 2018, p. 171). Lukyanchenko (2016) investigated the interrelation of professionally significant personal qualities and the working motivation of managers with their psychological well-being. The results of the study showed that “a productive attitude towards the work task, combined with a low focus on people and a high level of desired satisfaction with various aspects of work corresponds to higher levels of psychological well-being of managers.” Zausenko (2012), describing the psychological well-being of teachers, notes that “the reason for living of teachers is in the sphere of obvious usefulness to others, the value of their professional activities for others, at the same time there is a high degree of dependence on the environment and a feeling of powerlessness to change something in their profession”. As a part of our study, we consider the educational environment of the school at the regional level, studying the relationship of economic and educational factors with indicators of the psychological well-being of the teacher.

Methodology

Objective: to identify whether there is a difference in the indicators of psychological well-being of the teacher depending on the educational and economic rating of the school.

On the basis of statistical information posted on the official website of educational institutions of the Republic of Tatarstan, there were allocated two groups of municipal districts according to the criteria “maximum” expressed value by the parameters “economic school rating”, “educational school rating”.

The indicator “Economic school rating” includes the average salary of employees in the district where the school is located. In general, economically favorable and unfavorable districts were selected, and in order to exclude the influence of the location of the school (city-village), both city and village schools were taken. In this study, we selected schools from economically favorable areas.

The indicator "educational school rating" is an integral indicator. It includes the average grade that the school has on the Unified State Exam in Mathematics, the Russian language, a subject to choose from; the proportion of students who have not passed the Unified State Exam; the proportion of students participating in the Olympiad; the proportion of students who have passed the Unified State Exam with a score above 80 points.

Thus, in each of the selected districts two schools were studied, in total 127 teachers, 60 teachers from schools with a high economic rating (group 1), 67 teachers from schools with a high educational rating (group 2).

To solve research problems, the following diagnostic methods were used:

1) Questionnaire "WHOQOL-100" (the Russian version of which was validated by WHO in 2005). Quality of Life is considered by WHO as a multidimensional complex structure which includes the individual's perception of his/her physical and psychological state, level of independence, interpersonal relationships, personal convictions, as well as his/her attitude to significant characteristics of the environment. The life quality of the educational environment subjects is considered as an integral indicator for assessing the psychological well-being of its participants. With the help of the questionnaire, we assess the level of the respondent's well-being and subjective satisfaction with various aspects of life based on the analysis of six major spheres and 24 subspheres. The major spheres include "Physical Sphere", "Psychological Sphere", "Level of Independence", "Social Relations", "Environment", "Spiritual Sphere".

2) The AVEM questionnaire. The questionnaire allows you to describe the person's type of behavior in a professional environment. Interpretation of the questionnaire results involves taking into account the requirements of a particular professional sphere, in this case - pedagogical. Consequently, we are focused on the activity important qualities of the teacher, together with Povarenkov's definition (2018), we understand the activity important qualities as the individual qualities of a person that influence the efficiency of performing professional and meta-professional activities. The teacher while implementing an activity uses the resources and opportunities that he/she currently possesses at this level of professionalization: professional activity, mental resistance to problems and an emotional attitude to work.

The described spheres of personality and professional include three huge spheres and a number of scales. The scope of "Professional activity" includes 5 scales: Subjective value of activity (BA), Professional claims (BE), Readiness to energy loss (VB), Striving for excellence (PS), Ability to maintain a distance in relation to work (DF). The "Mental Resistance to Problems" sphere includes 3 scales: The tendency to refusal in a failure situation (RT), Active Problem Solving Strategy (OP), Inner calm and balance (IR). The "Emotional attitude to work" sphere includes 3 scales: Sense of success in professional activities (EE), Life satisfaction (LZ), Sense of social support (SU).

The research procedure included testing; there was used the statistical analysis program IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 (Student's t-test, r-Pearson's correlation analysis) for processing.

Results

Test for equality of the mean values of the studied indicators on the Student's t-test

On the first stage of our work there was checked the equality of the mean values of the two described groups on the Student's t-test. There were not found statistically significant differences in the described groups in terms of life quality. Thus, regardless of the school's economic or educational rating, teachers point to the same degree of satisfaction with their lives. Determining differences in the types of behavior of teachers in situations affecting the performance of professional and metaprofessional activities on the Student's t-test allowed us to record statistically significant differences on two scales: "The subjective value of activity" BA ($t = 2.879$, $p = 0.005$), "Active Problem Solving Strategy" OP ($t = 2.740$, $p = 0.007$). Both scales are significantly higher for teachers from schools of the 1st group. Accordingly, for teachers from high economic rating schools, the professional activity has a more significant place in life than for teachers from high educational rating schools. Moreover, teachers from high economic rating schools are characterized by an active and optimistic attitude towards emerging professional problems and tasks. At the same time, teachers from high educational rating schools are not always optimistic about professional problems and are not always ready to be engaged in their active solution.

Analysis of correlation relationships of the studied indicators

Analysis of the relationship between the life satisfaction and the type of teacher's behavior in the professional environment indicators shows a different number in the studied groups. The relationships of indicators with significant differences (according to Student's t-test) in the described groups attract particular interest. In the teachers group 1, "The subjective value of activity" BA ($r = 0.299$; with $p \leq 0.05$) is interrelated with the indicator "spiritual sphere" (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Correlation relationships of the indicator "BA"

Note: correlation at a significance level of 0.05.

correlation at a significance level of 0.01.

This sphere explores people's personal beliefs and how they affect their life quality and provide people with a certain sense of well-being. The presence of interrelation allows us to assume that teachers' personal

convictions help to cope with the difficulties of professional activity and maintain the importance of the profession at a high level. There were not recorded significant interrelations of this scale with life quality indicators in the second group of teachers.

The “Active Problem Solving Strategy” (OP) indicator in the first group has positive relationships with four of the six major spheres of life quality: “physical sphere” ($r = 0.341$; with $p \leq 0.01$), “level of independence” ($r = 0.257$ with $p \leq 0.05$), the sphere of “social interrelations” ($r = 0.325$; with $p \leq 0.05$), “the spiritual sphere” ($r = 0.406$; with $p \leq 0.01$) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Correlation relationships of the indicator “OP” of the teachers’ group 1
 Note: correlation at a significance level of 0.05.
 correlation at a significance level of 0.01.

Good physical well-being, the ability to cope with daily activities, not being dependent on anyone, a sense of support from other people, teachers' personal convictions will allow them to be optimistic about the emerging professional issues and tasks.

In the second group, this indicator also has positive relationships with the “physical sphere” ($r = 0.257$ with $p \leq 0.05$) and the sphere “level of independence” ($r = 0.335$; with $p \leq 0.01$); a relationship with “psychological sphere” ($r = 0.299$ with $p \leq 0.05$) has appeared (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Correlation relationships of the indicator “OP” of the teachers’ group 2
 Note: correlation at a significance level of 0.05.
 correlation at a significance level of 0.01.

With an increase in vitality and physical well-being, positive thoughts about oneself and the ability to be independent and self-sufficient the teacher will show an active strategy in solving professional problems. So, physical well-being, efficiency and independence in dealing with everyday issues make it possible for teachers to maintain a positive attitude to the arising professional problems, regardless of the rating of the school in which they work. However, for teachers from schools with a high economic rating, the emotional and physical support of a significant environment as well as personal beliefs, which are sources of a sense of well-being and security, are also important. And for teachers from schools with a high educational rating, an active and positive attitude towards solving professional problems is directly related to the psychological sphere, manifested in positive emotions, high self-esteem and the ability to learn new things.

Significant differences in the presence of relationships in the described groups are recorded on the "Inner calm and balance" IR scale, which describes a feeling of mental stability and balance. In group 1 this scale has a single positive relationship with the psychological sphere ($r = 0.329$ with $p \leq 0.05$) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Correlation relationships of the indicator "IR" of the teachers' group 1

Note: correlation at a significance level of 0.05.

correlation at a significance level of 0.01

The more teachers from high economic rate schools experiences positive feelings and a sense of inherent value, the more they are mentally stable in solving the emerging professional problems. Thus, for this group, a feeling of inner peace and balance is sufficient for psychological satisfaction with life. In group 2, the IR scale has positive relationships with all six existing life quality spheres: "physical sphere" ($r = 0.536$ with $p \leq 0.01$), "psychological sphere" ($r = 0.745$ with $p \leq 0.01$), "level of independence" ($r = 0.540$ with $p \leq 0.01$), "social relations" ($r = 0.244$ with $p \leq 0.05$), "environment" ($r = 0.486$ with $p \leq 0.01$), "spiritual sphere" ($r = 0.253$ with $p \leq 0.05$) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Correlation relationships of the indicator “IR” of the teachers’ group 2

Note: correlation at a significance level of 0.05.

correlation at a significance level of 0.01

For teachers from high educational rate schools , a feeling of inner peace and balance is possible with an increase in satisfaction with all aspects of life, including the individual's perception of their physical (the absence of fatigue and the presence of energy and strength, the possibility to recover sufficiently and relax) and psychological (the presence of positive or absence of negative emotions, the quality of thinking, memory or attention, adequate self-esteem, acceptance of one's appearance) state, level of independence (personal freedom, physical security, sense of security) , relationships with other people (the ability to support other people and get support from them) and personal convictions, as well as the attitude to the significant characteristics of their environment.

Discussions

According to our data, teachers from schools with a high economic rating have significantly higher values of the indicator on the “subjective value of activity” scale in comparison with indicators of teachers from schools with a high educational rating. Thus, the level of material income affects the degree of the subjective value of the activity. The obtained data correspond with the research of Bradburn (1969), who discovered the interdependence between the degree of psychological well-being and the level of material incomes.

Deci and Rayan (2008) relied in their work on understanding the phenomenon of “psychological well-being” based on the psycho-physiological preservation of functions. The authors suggested that personal well-being is associated with basic psychological needs: the need for autonomy, competence, and communication with others (Evans, 2006; Deci & Rayan, 2008; Kuznetsova, 2017). In our study, we have found that for teachers from schools with a high educational rating inner peace and a sense of mental stability are interconnected with all spheres of life, including the level of independence, personal freedom, physical safety and a sense of security, the ability to support other people and get support from them. The data obtained are consistent with the study of Zausenko (2012). The author, analyzing the indicators “Positive relationship with others” and “Self-acceptance”, indicates the teachers’ feelings about their

ability to establish close, trusting relationships with others. In our study, the indicator “Active Problem Solving Strategy”, for teachers from schools with a high economic rating, has the most interrelationships with areas of the teacher’s life that include intimate personal relationships, while having an opportunity to provide and maintain themselves.

According to the empirical research of Andronnikov and Veterok (2016), psychological well-being has direct correlations with the independence of the individual, self-development, meaningfulness of life, positive attitude, self-acceptance, management of the social environment, openness. Analysis of correlations in our study suggests that the studied "psychological sphere", "level of independence", "social relationships", "spiritual sphere", "physical sphere", "environment", which we consider as an integral indicator of psychological well-being, have a correlation relationships with the teacher’s professional activity (indicator "The subjective value of activity") and mental resistance to problems (indicators "Active strategy for solving problems", "Inner calm and balance").

Conclusion

Regardless of the school rating where the teachers work, they point to the same satisfaction with their lives.

For teachers from schools with a high economic rating, the subjective value of the profession is more significant than for teachers from schools with a high educational rating.

Mental resistance to problems is described in terms of the “Active Problem Solving Strategy” and “Inner Calm and Balance” scales. Regardless of the school rating, where the teachers work, physical well-being, ability to work, and autonomy in solving everyday issues allow them to maintain a positive attitude to the arising professional problems. At the same time, for teachers from schools with a high economic rating, social support of relatives and personal convictions, which are the source of a sense of well-being, safety and meaningfulness are also important. For teachers from schools with a high educational rating, an active and positive attitude to solving professional problems is directly connected with the psychological sphere manifested in positive emotions, reasonable self-esteem, ability to learn new things, acceptance of one’s appearance.

“Inner calm and balance”, for teachers from schools with a high economic rating are interconnected with one indicator - the “psychological sphere”, whereas, for teachers from schools with a high educational rating, this scale is interconnected with all spheres that characterize vital functions: physical, psychological sphere, level of independence, social relationships, environment, spiritual sphere. A sense of mental stability and resistance to professional problems of teachers group from schools with a high educational rating is possible in the condition of general psychological well-being.

Acknowledgements

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

References

- Andronnikova, O. O., & Veterok, E. V. (2016). Psychological well-being and health as an urgent need of a modern person within the framework of devictimization. *Bulletin of the Kemerovo State University*, 1(65), 72-76.
- Bagnetova, E. A., Pisareva, E. R., & Ponomareva, T. I. (2015). Professional factors of teachers' health and life quality. *Modern problems of science and education*, 5. Retrieved from <http://www.science-education.ru/en/article/view?id=21719>
- Bradburn N. M. (1969). *The structure of psychological well-being*. Chicago: Aldine.
- Cities rating. [online resource]. (2017). Retrieved from http://expert.ru/russian_reporter/2017/07/rejting-gorodov---2017/
- Deci E., & Ryan, R. (2008). Self-determination theory: A Macrotheory of Human Motivation, Development and Health. *Canadian Psychology*, 49(3), 182-185.
- Diener, E., Lucas, R., & Oishi, S. (2002). *Subjective well-being: The science of happiness and life satisfaction. The handbook of positive psychology*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L (1999). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125(2), 276-302.
- Evans, D. R. (2006). *The quality of life. In the book Psychological Encyclopedia*. Saint Petersburg: Peter.
- Filonenko, Yu. V., & Yakovleva, E. A. (2018). Factors and components of the subjective well-being of scientific and pedagogical workers of modern universities. *Journal of Economic Regulation*, 9(4), 160-177.

- Gilemkhanova, E. N. (2017). The interrelation of the predictors of students. *Quid-Investigacion Ciencia Y Tecnologia*, 28, 739-745.
- Gilemkhanova, E. N. (2019). The relationship of socio-psychological security and academic performance of the educational environment of municipalities. *Education and Self Development*. 14(2), 68-78.
- Ivanova, S. V. (2015). Educational space and educational environment: in search of differences. *Values and meanings*, 6, 40.
- Kuznetsova, E. S. Psychological well-being: theoretical approaches. *Psychological newspaper*. Retrieved from <https://psy.su/feed/6510/>
- Lukyanchenko, N. V. (2016). The relationship of professionally significant personal qualities and working motivation of managers with their psychological well-being. *Siberian Psychological Journal*, 62, 153–168.
- Pavlotskaya, Ya. I. (2016). *Psychological well-being and socio-psychological characteristics of the personality: monograph* [CD-ROM]. Volgograd: Publishing House of the Volgograd Institute of Management - branch of the Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration.
- Povarenkov, Yu. P. (2018). Definition and classification of activity-important qualities of a professional. System genesis of educational and professional activities. Part I. *Materials of the VIII All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference, [November 19-20, 2018] ed. prof. Yu. P. Povarenkova. Yaroslavl: EPU YSPU, 22-30.*
- Rating of Russian Federation regions by quality of life. (2016). Retrieved from http://vid1.rian.ru/ig/ratings/life_2016.pdf
- Rating of the best schools in Russia. (2017). Retrieved from <https://rg.ru/2017/10/04/nazvany-500-luchshih-shkol-rossii.html>
- Shiryaeva, O. S. (2008). *Psychological well-being of the individual in extreme conditions of life* (PhD dissertation). Khabarovsk: Vitus Bering Kamchatka State University.

Volkov, V. N. (2016). Ratings of Russian cities on the population life quality as a reflection of the effectiveness of educational systems. *Continuing Education: XXI Century (scientific electronic journal)*, 1(13), 54-62.

Zausenko, I. V. (2012). Psychological well-being of a teacher. *Pedagogical education in Russia*, 2, 28-31.